

Scientific theoretical basis of studying hydronyms in Uzbek and English languages

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Annotation: This article is about the English hydronyms, its origins, characteristics and types. The geographical names of the British Isles are quite well studied. These islands represent an area with clearly defined natural boundaries. The names that developed in England and the UK as a whole have become widespread in other countries where English is spoken.

Key words: hydronyms, toponyms, geographical names, linguistics, types structure.

In linguistics, hydronymy is a branch of onomastics or the process of thematic study of place names, which studies the names of basins associated with water, the origin of these names, and the history of their names. Hydronyms are a system that can include the names of rivers, lakes, seas, streams, and even ocean elements. HYDRONYM [hydro.. + wool. onyma - name] The name of the river, water bodies. In fact, the hydronym Murghab is related to the root "marg" in the Sughd language. "UTA". Hydronyms, which are part of onomastics, are distinguished by the fact that they have internal thematic divisions. According to linguists, every nation tries to preserve the original form of hydronyms. "For example, we can see that the Rhine River in Germany is not named in German, but in Celtic. The Mississippi River in the United States is named in the Anishinaabe language, not in French or English. The names of large rivers are more preserved than the names of small streams. Hydronymy can therefore be a means of reconstructing past cultural interactions, population movements, religious changes, or ancient languages. For example, Kenneth Jackson, a professor of history, found that some hydronymic names did not change as a result of the Anglo-Saxon invasion of Britain and the influence of English culture on the example of rivers.

The hydronymic location of territorially inland Britain can be seen to divide the island into three main areas of English settlement: the river valleys running eastwards, where surviving English hydronymic names are confined to the largest rivers, and the highlands, where Saxon settlement was early and dense. and the third region, where English hydronyms are located, is an area with smaller streams. Often,

a given body of water has several completely different names by the different peoples living along its shores. For example: the Mekong River in Southeast Asia has different names in Tibetan and Thai respectively. Hydronyms in different languages have a common etymology. For example, the Danube, Don, Dniester, Dnieper and Donets rivers all have the Scythian name for "river". In fact, we consider it appropriate to note that there are two different approaches to this issue. Some linguists note that toponyms can become hydronyms. For example, the River Liffey takes its name from the plain in which it is situated, called Life; the river itself was originally called An Ruirthech An unusual example is the River Cam - it was originally called the Granta, but when the town of Grantebreage became Cambridge, the river's name was changed to match the toponym. Based on the idea, one can see the process of turning toponyms into hydronyms not only in English, but also in other languages of the world.

It is known that the concept of hydronyms has a wide understanding and scope from the point of view of linguistics. Hydronomics is a branch of onomastics that studies the names of natural water bodies and water structures in a general sense. Hydronyms are nouns that name artificial and natural, large and small, as well as public water bodies and water structures. Professor N. Ulugov, who conducted a monographic study of hydronyms in Uzbek linguistics, reports that the names of water bodies and water structures form a separate semantic group - hydronyms - at the toponymic level of the Uzbek language, and they form 36 sub-thematic groups: 1) names of streams, 2) dam, dam, dam names, 3)swamp names, 4)spring, spring names, 5)hydrausel names, 6)hydroelectric power station names, 7)river names, 8)sea names, 9)yop names, 10)jilva names, 11) names of zakan, zovur, zakhkash, 12) names of tributaries / uzak, 13) names of canals, streams, 14) names of kechuv, 15) names of collectors, 16) names of koriz, 17) names of lakes, 18) names of bridges, 19) glacier names, 20) pumping station names, 21) oydin names, 22) olish names, 23) orel names, 24) ferry names, 25) cistern names, 26) selkhona names, 27) river names, 28) solma, yormish names . 28) Solma, Yormish names, 29) Soka names, 30) Reservoirs, 31) Tashlama, Kanda names, 32) Chungul names, 33) Waterfall names, 34) Waterfall names, 35) Well names, 36) Pool names. As mentioned above, if you pay attention to the units that make up these 36 hydronyms, you can see that the scale of the problem is really huge.

In world linguistics, especially in English linguistics, it can be seen that the study of hydronyms in a scientific-theoretical aspect is interpreted on the basis of 12 small thematic groups. We would like to pay attention to their naming, taking into account that each thematic group includes water names in a very broad sense. There are terms

that make up international hydronyms, such as Oceanonym, Pelagonim, Limnonim, Gelonim, Potamonym, Bathionim, Gymnonym, Speleonim, Geyser, Cascade, Glasionim, Insulonim.

Hydronyms in Uzbek linguistics and information related to their scientific study. Toponymist H. Hasanov's work "From the History of Central Asian Place Names" provides detailed theoretical information on hydronyms and oronyms and, especially, their naming features, while N. Begaliyev's "Hydronyms of the Samarkand Region" (1994) , "Historical-linguistic study of the hydronyms of the Uzbek language" (2010) by N.Ulukov can be evaluated as scientific-research works in the special direction of hydronyms.

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